

GRAMMATICAL MEANING AND GRAMMATICAL FORM

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Annotation. The article examines the grammatical meaning of a word as a phenomenon of vocabulary in linguistic literature. It is noted that grammatical meanings are external linguistic forms of expression that are common to a number of words. It is shown that in a word the lexical meaning (individual) and grammatical meaning (general) appear in dialectical unity.

Keywords: lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, relationship, abstractness, ways of expression

Introduction. Grammar is a component of linguistics, and its relationship with other fields of linguistics is multifaceted and complex. In the past, grammar was understood to teach the laws and rules that help us write and speak correctly. Today, the term grammar is used in two senses in linguistics. Grammar means, firstly, the grammatical construction of the language, and secondly, the science of the grammatical construction of the language. In the second sense, grammar is the science of the division of words into certain groups, the forms specific to each of them, and the grammatical construction of speech. It is known that language serves as a tool of exchange of ideas in human society. Every language must have a certain number of grammatical devices to enable people to communicate. But words alone are not enough to form a sentence. In a sentence, words are united based on the grammatical and phonetic rules of each language and express a certain idea. The grammatical structure of the language has its own categories and units. These are word forms, phrases and sentences. Grammar consists of two parts: morphology and syntax. Word groups, their categorial and non-categorial forms are studied in morphology. Syntax is the study of the grammatical structure of speech, which includes phrases, sentences, and larger units.

There are following types of grammar:

- historical grammar
- philosophical grammar
- general (universal) grammar
- comparative grammar
- visual grammar (descriptive)
- transformational grammar.

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Historical grammar studies the development of changes in the grammatical structure of a language. The main task of philosophical grammar is to study the communication possibilities of language and thinking, logical and grammatical categories. General grammar determines the common features and laws common to all languages, regardless of which language family they belong to. Comparative grammar compares and contrasts the grammatical systems of languages with each other, and studies their common and specific features. Comparative grammar, in turn, is divided into comparative-historical and typological-comparative grammars. Rasmus Rask (1787-1832) "Old Icelandic and the Emergence of the Icelandic Language". Ya. Grimm "Grammar of the German Language" (1819). Descriptive grammar studies the current (synchronous) state of the grammatical structure of a specific language. Descriptive grammar uses formal methods to determine language units and their meaning. In descriptive grammar, meaning is not taken into account in the process of analyzing the construction of language.

1. The basic notions of Grammar are the grammatical meaning, the grammatical form and the grammatical category. The grammatical meaning is a general, abstract meaning which embraces classes of words. The grammatical meaning depends on the lexical meaning and is connected with objective reality indirectly, through the lexical meaning. The grammatical meaning is relative, it is revealed in relations of word forms: *speak* — *speaks*. The grammatical meaning is obligatory. Grammatical meaning must be expressed if the speaker wants to be understood. The grammatical meaning must have a grammatical form of expression (inflexions, analytical forms, word-order, etc.). Compare the word forms *walks*, *is writing*. Both forms denote process, but only the second form expresses it grammatically.

2. In the system of language grammatical elements are connected on the basis of similarity and contrast. Partially similar elements, i.e. elements having common and distinctive features, constitute oppositions: *goes* — *went*, *table* — *tables*, *good* — *better* - *best*). Consider the opposition *table* — *tables*. Members of the opposition differ in form and have different grammatical meanings (singular and plural). At the same time they express the same general meaning — number. The unity of the general meaning and its particular manifestations which is revealed through the opposition of forms is a grammatical category. There may be different definitions of the category laying stress either on its notional or formal aspect. But the category exists only if there is an opposition of at least two forms. If there is one form, there is no category.

Conclusion. All grammatical forms of a word are sometimes divided into forms of inflection and forms of word formation, in this case including word formation in the section of grammar. This division goes back to F.F. Fortunatov. When changing words, the identity

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of the word is not violated. For example, in the Russian language, for nouns, inflection consists in changing them according to cases and numbers: oak - oak - oak - oak, oaks, etc. When word formation is made from one word, other words different from it are formed, for example: oak, dubnyak, oak. Morphological inflection is developed in different languages to varying degrees, for example, in East Slavic languages it is highly developed, in English it is weak, and in amorphous languages it may be completely absent.

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